

For Project: 13 Street S - 8 Avenue S to 9 Avenue S - NB
 Project Notes:
 Location/Name: Incoming - Northbound
 Report Generated: 11/25/2022 11:13
 Speed Intervals 1 km/h
 Time Intervals Instant
 Traffic Report From 11/22/2022 00:00:00 through
 85th Percentile Speed 58 km/h
 85th Percentile Vehicles 13185
 Max Speed 110 km/h on 11/23/2022
 Total Vehicles 15512
 AADT: 5170

Volumes - weekly counts

Time	5 Day
Average Daily	5170
AM Peak 07:45	402
PM Peak 03:15	488

Speed

Speed Limit: 50
 85th Percentile Speed: 58
 50th Percentile Speed: 53
 10 km/h Pace Interval: 48.0 km/h to 58.0 km/h
 Average Speed: 53.04

	Monday	Tuesday	Wednesday
Count over limit	N/A	3694	3448
% over limit	N/A	69.7	68.3
Avg Speeder	N/A	55.7	55.7

Class Counts

	Number	%
VEH_SM	31	0.2
VEH_MED	15105	97.4
VEH_LG	376	2.4
[VEH_SM=motorcycle,	VEH_MED = sedan,	VEH_LG = tri

Day/Time Ending	85th pctl (km/h)	85th pctl cnts	Total Cnts
11/22/2022 01:00:00 AM	60.0	17	20
11/22/2022 02:00:00 AM	56.0	10	12
11/22/2022 03:00:00 AM	58.0	11	13
11/22/2022 04:00:00 AM	62.0	11	13
11/22/2022 05:00:00 AM	60.0	12	14
11/22/2022 06:00:00 AM	60.0	61	72
11/22/2022 07:00:00 AM	59.0	113	133
11/22/2022 08:00:00 AM	57.0	309	363
11/22/2022 09:00:00 AM	59.0	352	414
11/22/2022 10:00:00 AM	59.0	267	314
11/22/2022 11:00:00 AM	59.0	246	290

11/22/2022 12:00:00 PM	59.0	269	317
11/22/2022 01:00:00 PM	59.0	326	384
11/22/2022 02:00:00 PM	58.0	321	378
11/22/2022 03:00:00 PM	59.0	323	380
11/22/2022 04:00:00 PM	57.0	404	475
11/22/2022 05:00:00 PM	58.0	401	472
11/22/2022 06:00:00 PM	56.0	290	341
11/22/2022 07:00:00 PM	57.0	223	262
11/22/2022 08:00:00 PM	58.0	168	198
11/22/2022 09:00:00 PM	57.0	131	154
11/22/2022 10:00:00 PM	58.0	86	101
11/22/2022 11:00:00 PM	58.0	72	85
11/23/2022 12:00:00 AM	58.0	82	96
11/23/2022 01:00:00 AM	56.0	16	19
11/23/2022 02:00:00 AM	56.0	8	10
11/23/2022 03:00:00 AM	56.0	8	10
11/23/2022 04:00:00 AM	61.0	7	8
11/23/2022 05:00:00 AM	56.0	16	19
11/23/2022 06:00:00 AM	59.0	48	56
11/23/2022 07:00:00 AM	57.0	96	113
11/23/2022 08:00:00 AM	57.0	265	312
11/23/2022 09:00:00 AM	58.0	292	343
11/23/2022 10:00:00 AM	58.0	244	287
11/23/2022 11:00:00 AM	58.0	260	306
11/23/2022 12:00:00 PM	58.0	262	308
11/23/2022 01:00:00 PM	59.0	301	354
11/23/2022 02:00:00 PM	58.0	281	331
11/23/2022 03:00:00 PM	58.0	353	415
11/23/2022 04:00:00 PM	57.0	391	460
11/23/2022 05:00:00 PM	58.0	365	429
11/23/2022 06:00:00 PM	57.0	289	340
11/23/2022 07:00:00 PM	58.0	247	291
11/23/2022 08:00:00 PM	57.0	172	202
11/23/2022 09:00:00 PM	58.0	142	167
11/23/2022 10:00:00 PM	58.0	92	108
11/23/2022 11:00:00 PM	58.0	60	71
11/24/2022 12:00:00 AM	59.0	75	88
11/24/2022 01:00:00 AM	59.0	21	25
11/24/2022 02:00:00 AM	59.0	9	11
11/24/2022 03:00:00 AM	60.0	9	11
11/24/2022 04:00:00 AM	60.0	14	16
11/24/2022 05:00:00 AM	60.0	19	22
11/24/2022 06:00:00 AM	61.0	42	50
11/24/2022 07:00:00 AM	59.0	97	114
11/24/2022 08:00:00 AM	58.0	280	329
11/24/2022 09:00:00 AM	58.0	272	320
11/24/2022 10:00:00 AM	59.0	252	297
11/24/2022 11:00:00 AM	59.0	270	318
11/24/2022 12:00:00 PM	60.0	284	334
11/24/2022 01:00:00 PM	59.0	297	349
11/24/2022 02:00:00 PM	58.0	307	361
11/24/2022 03:00:00 PM	60.0	324	381

11/24/2022 04:00:00 PM	58.0	429	505
11/24/2022 05:00:00 PM	58.0	417	491
11/24/2022 06:00:00 PM	57.0	299	352
11/24/2022 07:00:00 PM	58.0	222	261
11/24/2022 08:00:00 PM	58.0	175	206
11/24/2022 09:00:00 PM	58.0	124	146
11/24/2022 10:00:00 PM	60.0	91	107
11/24/2022 11:00:00 PM	60.0	60	70
11/25/2022 12:00:00 AM	59.0	75	88

Day/Time Ending	85th pctl (km/h)	85th pctl cnts	Total Cnts
11/23/2022 12:00:00 AM	58.0	4506	5301
11/24/2022 12:00:00 AM	58.0	4290	5047
11/24/2022 11:59:59 PM	59.0	4389	5164

11/24/2022

23:59:59

14:41:23

7 Day

5170

402

488

Thursday

Friday

Saturday

3760

N/A

N/A

72.8

N/A

N/A

55.8

N/A

N/A

uck]

Max Speed

Avg Speeder

% Speeders

65

57.3

65.0%

67

56.4

58.3%

64

56.9

53.8%

62

59.4

76.9%

83

58.8

64.3%

68

56.6

73.6%

77

56.8

79.7%

102

56.0

61.4%

72

55.5

78.0%

79

55.8

74.8%

69

56.0

75.2%

67	56.0	78.9%
70	55.9	71.1%
68	55.8	74.3%
76	55.9	73.2%
74	55.2	67.2%
85	55.2	69.7%
69	54.7	58.9%
70	55.1	63.4%
77	55.8	55.6%
78	55.5	66.2%
68	55.5	66.3%
71	56.2	60.0%
81	55.7	65.6%
65	55.5	57.9%
60	55.4	70.0%
71	58.0	60.0%
68	62.3	50.0%
72	56.4	68.4%
65	56.9	58.9%
64	55.0	59.3%
73	55.2	58.7%
76	56.0	67.3%
80	55.5	79.8%
71	55.7	66.0%
71	55.7	72.4%
81	55.9	72.3%
79	55.6	72.5%
110	56.0	72.0%
69	55.4	64.6%
70	55.5	73.9%
70	55.4	63.8%
87	55.7	68.0%
69	55.2	65.3%
70	55.9	62.3%
71	55.9	66.7%
71	56.2	64.8%
70	56.3	69.3%
68	56.0	80.0%
65	56.4	90.9%
61	55.4	72.7%
63	56.2	81.3%
84	57.9	81.8%
68	57.4	80.0%
69	56.6	78.9%
84	55.6	68.1%
69	55.3	69.7%
78	56.1	76.8%
70	55.7	72.0%
71	56.3	80.2%
73	56.1	74.5%
72	55.7	76.2%
72	55.9	74.5%

74	55.7	71.9%
74	55.2	70.3%
79	55.2	68.5%
79	55.5	69.3%
77	55.4	67.5%
73	56.0	71.9%
80	56.5	74.8%
68	56.8	74.3%
71	56.7	72.7%

Max Speed	Avg Speeder	% Speeders
102	55.7	69.7%
110	55.7	68.3%
84	55.8	72.8%

Sunday

N/A

N/A

N/A

Incoming Weekly Counts

13 Street S - 8 Avenue S to 9 Avenue S - NB

from Tue-Nov-22-202

Hour	11/21/2022	to	11/27/2022		
	Monday	Tuesday	Wednesday	Thursday	Friday
	11/21/2022	11/22/2022	11/23/2022	11/24/2022	11/25/2022
0 - 1	0	20	19	25	0
1 - 2	0	12	10	11	0
2 - 3	0	13	10	11	0
3 - 4	0	13	8	16	0
4 - 5	0	14	19	22	0
5 - 6	0	72	56	50	0
6 - 7	0	133	113	114	0
7 - 8	0	363	312	329	0
8 - 9	0	414	343	320	0
9 - 10	0	314	287	297	0
10 - 11	0	290	306	318	0
11 - 12	0	317	308	334	0
12 - 13	0	384	354	349	0
13 - 14	0	378	331	361	0
14 - 15	0	380	415	381	0
15 - 16	0	475	460	505	0
16 - 17	0	472	429	491	0
17 - 18	0	341	340	352	0
18 - 19	0	262	291	261	0
19 - 20	0	198	202	206	0
20 - 21	0	154	167	146	0
21 - 22	0	101	108	107	0
22 - 23	0	85	71	70	0
23 - 24	0	96	88	88	0
Totals	0	5301	5047	5164	0
% of Total	0%	34.17%	32.54%	33.29%	0%

Saturday	Sunday	Week	Weekend	Week Day 85%
11/26/2022	11/27/2022	Day Avg	Avg	Avg Speed
0	0	21.33	0	58.33
0	0	11	0	57
0	0	11.33	0	57.83
0	0	12.33	0	60.77
0	0	18.33	0	58.67
0	0	59.33	0	59.5
0	0	120	0	58.03
0	0	334.67	0	56.73
0	0	359	0	57.83
0	0	299.33	0	58.23
0	0	304.67	0	58.13
0	0	319.67	0	58.7
0	0	362.33	0	58.4
0	0	356.67	0	57.7
0	0	392	0	58.47
0	0	480	0	57.2
0	0	464	0	57.53
0	0	344.33	0	56.47
0	0	271.33	0	57.07
0	0	202	0	57.2
0	0	155.67	0	57.53
0	0	105.33	0	58.37
0	0	75.33	0	58.23
0	0	90.67	0	58.37
0	0			
0%	0%			

Incoming Monthly Counts

13 Street S - 8 Avenue S to 9 Avenue S - NB

from Tue-Nov-22-2022-12-00-AM

Hour	Nov 2022					
	Monday	Tuesday	Wednesday	Thursday	Friday	Saturday
0 - 1	0	20	19	25	0	0
1 - 2	0	12	10	11	0	0
2 - 3	0	13	10	11	0	0
3 - 4	0	13	8	16	0	0
4 - 5	0	14	19	22	0	0
5 - 6	0	72	56	50	0	0
6 - 7	0	133	113	114	0	0
7 - 8	0	363	312	329	0	0
8 - 9	0	414	343	320	0	0
9 - 10	0	314	287	297	0	0
10 - 11	0	290	306	318	0	0
11 - 12	0	317	308	334	0	0
12 - 13	0	384	354	349	0	0
13 - 14	0	378	331	361	0	0
14 - 15	0	380	415	381	0	0
15 - 16	0	475	460	505	0	0
16 - 17	0	472	429	491	0	0
17 - 18	0	341	340	352	0	0
18 - 19	0	262	291	261	0	0
19 - 20	0	198	202	206	0	0
20 - 21	0	154	167	146	0	0
21 - 22	0	101	108	107	0	0
22 - 23	0	85	71	70	0	0
23 - 24	0	96	88	88	0	0
Totals	0	5301	5047	5164	0	0
% of Total	0%	20.33%	19.36%	19.81%	0%	0%

Sunday	Week Day Avg	Weekend Avg	Week Day 85% Avg Speed
0	21.33	0	58.33
0	11	0	57
0	11.33	0	57.83
0	12.33	0	60.77
0	18.33	0	58.67
0	59.33	0	59.5
0	120	0	58.03
0	334.67	0	56.73
0	359	0	57.83
0	299.33	0	58.23
0	304.67	0	58.13
0	319.67	0	58.7
0	362.33	0	58.4
0	356.67	0	57.7
0	392	0	58.47
0	480	0	57.2
0	464	0	57.53
0	344.33	0	56.47
0	271.33	0	57.07
0	202	0	57.2
0	155.67	0	57.53
0	105.33	0	58.37
0	75.33	0	58.23
0	90.67	0	58.37
0			
0%			

Incoming Weekly Speeds

13 Street S - 8 Avenue S to 9 Avenue S - NB

from Tue-Nov-22-202

Hour	11/21/2022	to	11/27/2022		
	Monday	Tuesday	Wednesday	Thursday	Friday
	11/21/2022	11/22/2022	11/23/2022	11/24/2022	11/25/2022
0 - 1	0	53.85	51.89	54.04	0
1 - 2	0	52.33	52.9	55.55	0
2 - 3	0	51.85	52.7	52.36	0
3 - 4	0	56.54	54.5	54.94	0
4 - 5	0	55.14	52.95	54.73	0
5 - 6	0	54.31	51.79	55.48	0
6 - 7	0	54.92	51.39	54.75	0
7 - 8	0	52.2	51.37	52.66	0
8 - 9	0	53.57	52.85	52.67	0
9 - 10	0	53.63	53.89	54.09	0
10 - 11	0	53.84	52.65	53.19	0
11 - 12	0	54.03	53.38	54.65	0
12 - 13	0	53.33	53.32	53.85	0
13 - 14	0	53.58	53.26	53.63	0
14 - 15	0	53.41	53.36	53.7	0
15 - 16	0	52.35	52.57	52.94	0
16 - 17	0	52.61	53.14	52.81	0
17 - 18	0	51.34	51.93	52.5	0
18 - 19	0	52.19	52.85	52.54	0
19 - 20	0	51.89	52.2	52.53	0
20 - 21	0	52.27	52.49	53.16	0
21 - 22	0	52.56	52.66	53.9	0
22 - 23	0	51.96	52.85	54.13	0
23 - 24	0	52.54	53.23	54.05	0
Totals	0	1275.9	1266.3	1288.6	0
% of Total	0%	33.31%	33.06%	33.64%	0%

Saturday	Sunday	Week	Weekend	Week Day 85%
11/26/2022	11/27/2022	Day Avg	Avg	Avg Speed
0	0	53.34	0	58.33
0	0	53.58	0	57
0	0	52.26	0	57.83
0	0	55.41	0	60.77
0	0	54.22	0	58.67
0	0	53.84	0	59.5
0	0	53.76	0	58.03
0	0	52.09	0	56.73
0	0	53.07	0	57.83
0	0	53.87	0	58.23
0	0	53.22	0	58.13
0	0	54.04	0	58.7
0	0	53.49	0	58.4
0	0	53.5	0	57.7
0	0	53.49	0	58.47
0	0	52.62	0	57.2
0	0	52.84	0	57.53
0	0	51.93	0	56.47
0	0	52.54	0	57.07
0	0	52.21	0	57.2
0	0	52.63	0	57.53
0	0	53.05	0	58.37
0	0	52.91	0	58.23
0	0	53.25	0	58.37
0	0			
0%	0%			

Incoming Monthly Speeds

13 Street S - 8 Avenue S to 9 Avenue S - NB

from Tue-Nov-22-2022-12-00-AM to Thu-Nov-

Hour	Nov 2022						
	Monday	Tuesday	Wednesday	Thursday	Friday	Saturday	Sunday
0 - 1	0	53.85	51.89	54.04	0	0	0
1 - 2	0	52.33	52.9	55.55	0	0	0
2 - 3	0	51.85	52.7	52.36	0	0	0
3 - 4	0	56.54	54.5	54.94	0	0	0
4 - 5	0	55.14	52.95	54.73	0	0	0
5 - 6	0	54.31	51.79	55.48	0	0	0
6 - 7	0	54.92	51.39	54.75	0	0	0
7 - 8	0	52.2	51.37	52.66	0	0	0
8 - 9	0	53.57	52.85	52.67	0	0	0
9 - 10	0	53.63	53.89	54.09	0	0	0
10 - 11	0	53.84	52.65	53.19	0	0	0
11 - 12	0	54.03	53.38	54.65	0	0	0
12 - 13	0	53.33	53.32	53.85	0	0	0
13 - 14	0	53.58	53.26	53.63	0	0	0
14 - 15	0	53.41	53.36	53.7	0	0	0
15 - 16	0	52.35	52.57	52.94	0	0	0
16 - 17	0	52.61	53.14	52.81	0	0	0
17 - 18	0	51.34	51.93	52.5	0	0	0
18 - 19	0	52.19	52.85	52.54	0	0	0
19 - 20	0	51.89	52.2	52.53	0	0	0
20 - 21	0	52.27	52.49	53.16	0	0	0
21 - 22	0	52.56	52.66	53.9	0	0	0
22 - 23	0	51.96	52.85	54.13	0	0	0
23 - 24	0	52.54	53.23	54.05	0	0	0

Week	Weekend	Week Day 85%
Day Avg	Avg	Avg Speed
53.34	0	58.33
53.58	0	57
52.26	0	57.83
55.41	0	60.77
54.22	0	58.67
53.84	0	59.5
53.76	0	58.03
52.09	0	56.73
53.07	0	57.83
53.87	0	58.23
53.22	0	58.13
54.04	0	58.7
53.49	0	58.4
53.5	0	57.7
53.49	0	58.47
52.62	0	57.2
52.84	0	57.53
51.93	0	56.47
52.54	0	57.07
52.21	0	57.2
52.63	0	57.53
53.05	0	58.37
52.91	0	58.23
53.25	0	58.37

Incoming Weekly EightyFifthSpeeds
 13 Street S - 8 Avenue S to 9 Avenue S - NB

from Tue-Nov-22-202

Hour	11/21/2022	to	11/27/2022		
	Monday 11/21/2022	Tuesday 11/22/2022	Wednesday 11/23/2022	Thursday 11/24/2022	Friday 11/25/2022
0 - 1	0	60	56	59	0
1 - 2	0	56	56	59	0
2 - 3	0	58	56	59.5	0
3 - 4	0	61.3	61	60	0
4 - 5	0	60	56	60	0
5 - 6	0	59.5	58.5	60.5	0
6 - 7	0	58.9	56.5	58.7	0
7 - 8	0	56.9	56.2	57.1	0
8 - 9	0	58.2	57.9	57.4	0
9 - 10	0	58.4	57.8	58.5	0
10 - 11	0	58.4	57.8	58.2	0
11 - 12	0	58.7	57.9	59.5	0
12 - 13	0	58.2	58.2	58.8	0
13 - 14	0	57.9	57.6	57.6	0
14 - 15	0	58.4	58	59	0
15 - 16	0	56.7	57	57.9	0
16 - 17	0	57.1	58	57.5	0
17 - 18	0	55.8	56.7	56.9	0
18 - 19	0	56.6	57.5	57.1	0
19 - 20	0	57.4	56.9	57.3	0
20 - 21	0	57	57.6	58	0
21 - 22	0	58	57.5	59.6	0
22 - 23	0	57.4	57.3	60	0
23 - 24	0	57.5	58.8	58.8	0
Totals	0	1392.3	1378.7	1405.9	0
% of Total	0%	33.33%	33.01%	33.66%	0%

Saturday	Sunday	Week	Weekend	Week Day 85%
11/26/2022	11/27/2022	Day Avg	Avg	Avg Speed
0	0	58.33	0	58.33
0	0	57	0	57
0	0	57.83	0	57.83
0	0	60.77	0	60.77
0	0	58.67	0	58.67
0	0	59.5	0	59.5
0	0	58.03	0	58.03
0	0	56.73	0	56.73
0	0	57.83	0	57.83
0	0	58.23	0	58.23
0	0	58.13	0	58.13
0	0	58.7	0	58.7
0	0	58.4	0	58.4
0	0	57.7	0	57.7
0	0	58.47	0	58.47
0	0	57.2	0	57.2
0	0	57.53	0	57.53
0	0	56.47	0	56.47
0	0	57.07	0	57.07
0	0	57.2	0	57.2
0	0	57.53	0	57.53
0	0	58.37	0	58.37
0	0	58.23	0	58.23
0	0	58.37	0	58.37
0	0			
0%	0%			

Incoming Monthly EightyFifthSpeeds
 13 Street S - 8 Avenue S to 9 Avenue S - NB

from Tue-Nov-22-2022-12-00-AM to Thu-Nov-

Hour	Nov 2022						
	Monday	Tuesday	Wednesday	Thursday	Friday	Saturday	Sunday
0 - 1	0	60	56	59	0	0	0
1 - 2	0	56	56	59	0	0	0
2 - 3	0	58	56	59.5	0	0	0
3 - 4	0	61.3	61	60	0	0	0
4 - 5	0	60	56	60	0	0	0
5 - 6	0	59.5	58.5	60.5	0	0	0
6 - 7	0	58.9	56.5	58.7	0	0	0
7 - 8	0	56.9	56.2	57.1	0	0	0
8 - 9	0	58.2	57.9	57.4	0	0	0
9 - 10	0	58.4	57.8	58.5	0	0	0
10 - 11	0	58.4	57.8	58.2	0	0	0
11 - 12	0	58.7	57.9	59.5	0	0	0
12 - 13	0	58.2	58.2	58.8	0	0	0
13 - 14	0	57.9	57.6	57.6	0	0	0
14 - 15	0	58.4	58	59	0	0	0
15 - 16	0	56.7	57	57.9	0	0	0
16 - 17	0	57.1	58	57.5	0	0	0
17 - 18	0	55.8	56.7	56.9	0	0	0
18 - 19	0	56.6	57.5	57.1	0	0	0
19 - 20	0	57.4	56.9	57.3	0	0	0
20 - 21	0	57	57.6	58	0	0	0
21 - 22	0	58	57.5	59.6	0	0	0
22 - 23	0	57.4	57.3	60	0	0	0
23 - 24	0	57.5	58.8	58.8	0	0	0

Week	Weekend	Week Day 85%
Day Avg	Avg	Avg Speed
58.33	0	58.33
57	0	57
57.83	0	57.83
60.77	0	60.77
58.67	0	58.67
59.5	0	59.5
58.03	0	58.03
56.73	0	56.73
57.83	0	57.83
58.23	0	58.23
58.13	0	58.13
58.7	0	58.7
58.4	0	58.4
57.7	0	57.7
58.47	0	58.47
57.2	0	57.2
57.53	0	57.53
56.47	0	56.47
57.07	0	57.07
57.2	0	57.2
57.53	0	57.53
58.37	0	58.37
58.23	0	58.23
58.37	0	58.37

RADAR MOTOR VEHICLE SPEED

Date: 11/22/2022 County: [redacted] Hwy: [redacted] Location: [redacted]
 Time (from): 12:00 AM (to): 11:59 PM Weather: [redacted]
 Surface Type: [redacted] Surface Condition: [redacted] Wet: [redacted] Dry: [redacted] Smo: [redacted]

km/h	AUTOMOBILES Direction:	Cumulative Total	AUTOMOBILES Direction:	Cumulative Total	TRUCKS Direction:
>= 80		14			
79		18			
78		21			
77		24			
76		28			
75		29			
74		33			
73		37			
72		46			
71		71			
70		92			
69		121			
68		160			
67		201			
66		270			
65		373			
64		505			
63		645			
62		874			
61		1237			

55

5976

54

7063

53

8356

52

9705

51

10902

50

11852

49

12704

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48

13420

|||||

47

13978

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46

14366

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45

14653

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44

14901

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43

15078

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42

15177

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41

15256

|

40

15313

|||||

15512

x 0.85

x 0.85

85th Percentile Vehicles (counts)

13185

85th Percentile Vehicles (counts)

85th Percentile Speed

58

85th Percentile Speed

Form 1882
(Rev. 03/19)

oth: Rough:

& BUSES Direction:	km/h
	>= 80
	79
	78
	77
	76
	75
	74
	73
	72
	71
	70
	69
	68
	67
	66
	65
	64
	63
	62
	61

55

54

53

52

51

50

	39
	38
	37
	36
	35
	34
	33
	32
	31
	<= 30

Starting Hour	Count	Average Speed of all Traffic	Violator Counts	Average Speed of Violators
00:00:00	17	52.4	10	55.4
00:15:00	15	54.8	12	57.3
00:30:00	17	54.4	13	56.5
00:45:00	15	51.7	9	55.6
01:00:00	12	54.5	9	56.7
01:15:00	3	50.7	1	52.0
01:30:00	12	54.2	9	57.1
01:45:00	6	52.0	5	54.2
02:00:00	8	53.9	5	58.2
02:15:00	10	54.2	7	57.9
02:30:00	11	50.8	6	55.7
02:45:00	5	49.0	3	53.0
03:00:00	7	57.3	6	58.8
03:15:00	7	57.4	6	59.2
03:30:00	15	54.1	10	57.5
03:45:00	8	54.4	5	58.2
04:00:00	5	50.4	3	54.0
04:15:00	15	54.1	11	58.4
04:30:00	13	52.2	9	54.0
04:45:00	22	56.4	17	59.7
05:00:00	28	52.0	16	57.1
05:15:00	49	55.6	38	58.2
05:30:00	35	53.6	25	56.6
05:45:00	66	53.4	47	56.1
06:00:00	36	53.9	31	55.5
06:15:00	72	52.8	48	56.1
06:30:00	115	54.0	83	56.6
06:45:00	137	54.0	101	56.3
07:00:00	143	51.7	89	55.2
07:15:00	185	52.4	127	55.3
07:30:00	284	52.0	175	55.6
07:45:00	392	52.2	239	55.9
08:00:00	268	52.9	183	55.6
08:15:00	247	53.1	176	55.9
08:30:00	299	53.0	219	55.5
08:45:00	263	53.4	199	55.6
09:00:00	187	54.4	151	55.9
09:15:00	206	54.0	162	56.0
09:30:00	227	53.8	167	56.1
09:45:00	278	53.5	212	55.4
10:00:00	238	53.3	166	56.3
10:15:00	214	53.0	146	55.7
10:30:00	215	53.5	159	55.8
10:45:00	247	53.1	178	55.4
11:00:00	212	53.6	158	55.9
11:15:00	241	54.1	179	56.3
11:30:00	242	53.7	188	55.7
11:45:00	264	54.6	216	56.2
12:00:00	267	54.1	205	56.2
12:15:00	252	53.6	177	56.5
12:30:00	263	53.2	190	55.5
12:45:00	305	53.1	217	55.7
13:00:00	289	53.2	218	55.2

13:15:00	254	54.1	193	56.3
13:30:00	252	53.5	180	56.1
13:45:00	275	53.2	205	55.4
14:00:00	284	53.6	203	56.2
14:15:00	311	53.6	235	56.0
14:30:00	298	53.6	216	56.0
14:45:00	283	53.2	207	55.5
15:00:00	336	52.5	233	55.2
15:15:00	382	53.1	265	55.5
15:30:00	347	52.4	232	55.8
15:45:00	375	52.4	249	55.2
16:00:00	362	53.1	264	55.7
16:15:00	378	52.9	282	54.8
16:30:00	332	53.1	241	55.4
16:45:00	320	52.3	204	55.4
17:00:00	305	51.4	183	55.0
17:15:00	267	51.9	174	54.8
17:30:00	240	52.7	162	55.6
17:45:00	221	51.8	140	55.0
18:00:00	235	52.1	154	55.2
18:15:00	225	52.1	147	55.1
18:30:00	163	52.9	109	55.9
18:45:00	191	53.4	135	55.7
19:00:00	184	51.6	115	54.9
19:15:00	176	52.8	116	55.6
19:30:00	139	51.8	81	55.5
19:45:00	107	52.9	69	56.2
20:00:00	136	52.5	90	55.2
20:15:00	114	53.5	80	56.2
20:30:00	96	52.5	65	55.8
20:45:00	121	52.1	76	56.0
21:00:00	110	53.1	76	56.1
21:15:00	84	52.2	57	55.6
21:30:00	60	53.0	42	55.5
21:45:00	62	54.1	44	56.9
22:00:00	62	52.7	39	56.4
22:15:00	58	53.2	40	56.9
22:30:00	45	52.6	28	56.0
22:45:00	61	53.1	42	56.3
23:00:00	83	52.7	56	55.5
23:15:00	96	52.9	63	56.5
23:30:00	44	53.8	32	56.7
23:45:00	49	54.3	37	56.6

Incoming Histogram

13 Street S - 8 Avenue S to 9 Avenue S - NB

Date	Starting Hr:min	<15	15 to <20	20 to <25	25 to <30	30 to <35	35 to <40	40 to <45
11/22/2022	00:00	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11/22/2022	00:15	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
11/22/2022	00:30	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11/22/2022	00:45	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11/22/2022	01:00	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11/22/2022	01:15	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11/22/2022	01:30	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
11/22/2022	01:45	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11/22/2022	02:00	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11/22/2022	02:15	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11/22/2022	02:30	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11/22/2022	02:45	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
11/22/2022	03:00	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11/22/2022	03:15	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11/22/2022	03:30	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11/22/2022	03:45	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
11/22/2022	04:00	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11/22/2022	04:15	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11/22/2022	04:30	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11/22/2022	04:45	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11/22/2022	05:00	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
11/22/2022	05:15	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11/22/2022	05:30	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11/22/2022	05:45	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11/22/2022	06:00	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11/22/2022	06:15	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
11/22/2022	06:30	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11/22/2022	06:45	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
11/22/2022	07:00	0	0	0	0	1	3	3
11/22/2022	07:15	0	0	0	1	0	0	2
11/22/2022	07:30	0	0	0	0	0	0	14
11/22/2022	07:45	0	0	1	1	1	0	10
11/22/2022	08:00	0	0	0	0	0	3	5
11/22/2022	08:15	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
11/22/2022	08:30	0	0	0	0	0	0	4
11/22/2022	08:45	0	0	0	0	0	1	4
11/22/2022	09:00	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
11/22/2022	09:15	0	0	0	0	0	0	6
11/22/2022	09:30	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
11/22/2022	09:45	0	0	0	0	0	1	7
11/22/2022	10:00	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
11/22/2022	10:15	0	0	0	0	0	3	3
11/22/2022	10:30	0	0	0	0	1	1	0
11/22/2022	10:45	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11/22/2022	11:00	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
11/22/2022	11:15	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
11/22/2022	11:30	0	1	0	0	0	0	2
11/22/2022	11:45	0	0	0	0	1	0	1
11/22/2022	12:00	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
11/22/2022	12:15	0	0	0	0	0	1	3

11/22/2022	12:30	0	0	0	0	0	0	6
11/22/2022	12:45	1	0	0	0	0	0	6
11/22/2022	13:00	0	0	0	0	0	0	3
11/22/2022	13:15	0	0	0	0	0	0	4
11/22/2022	13:30	0	0	0	0	0	0	4
11/22/2022	13:45	0	0	0	0	0	0	4
11/22/2022	14:00	0	0	0	0	0	0	4
11/22/2022	14:15	0	1	0	0	0	1	6
11/22/2022	14:30	0	0	0	0	0	0	4
11/22/2022	14:45	0	0	0	0	0	1	2
11/22/2022	15:00	0	0	0	0	1	1	7
11/22/2022	15:15	0	0	0	0	0	2	7
11/22/2022	15:30	0	0	0	0	1	1	8
11/22/2022	15:45	0	0	0	0	1	2	5
11/22/2022	16:00	1	0	0	0	0	0	6
11/22/2022	16:15	0	0	0	0	0	0	4
11/22/2022	16:30	0	0	0	0	0	1	7
11/22/2022	16:45	0	0	0	0	0	0	11
11/22/2022	17:00	0	0	0	0	0	2	11
11/22/2022	17:15	0	0	0	0	1	1	4
11/22/2022	17:30	0	0	0	0	0	3	7
11/22/2022	17:45	0	0	0	0	1	1	1
11/22/2022	18:00	0	0	0	0	0	0	7
11/22/2022	18:15	0	0	0	0	0	0	4
11/22/2022	18:30	0	0	0	0	0	0	3
11/22/2022	18:45	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11/22/2022	19:00	1	0	0	0	0	0	1
11/22/2022	19:15	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
11/22/2022	19:30	0	0	0	0	0	0	4
11/22/2022	19:45	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
11/22/2022	20:00	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11/22/2022	20:15	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
11/22/2022	20:30	0	0	0	0	0	1	3
11/22/2022	20:45	1	0	0	0	0	3	1
11/22/2022	21:00	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
11/22/2022	21:15	0	0	0	1	0	0	1
11/22/2022	21:30	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11/22/2022	21:45	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
11/22/2022	22:00	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
11/22/2022	22:15	0	1	0	0	0	0	3
11/22/2022	22:30	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
11/22/2022	22:45	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
11/22/2022	23:00	0	0	0	0	0	0	3
11/22/2022	23:15	0	0	0	0	1	0	4
11/22/2022	23:30	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
11/22/2022	23:45	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
24 Hr Summary		4	3	1	3	10	35	251

Date	Starting Hr:min	<15	15 to <20	20 to <25	25 to <30	30 to <35	35 to <40	40 to <45
11/23/2022	00:00	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11/23/2022	00:15	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11/23/2022	00:30	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
11/23/2022	00:45	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
11/23/2022	01:00	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

11/23/2022	01:15	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11/23/2022	01:30	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11/23/2022	01:45	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
11/23/2022	02:00	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11/23/2022	02:15	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
11/23/2022	02:30	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
11/23/2022	02:45	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11/23/2022	03:00	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11/23/2022	03:15	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11/23/2022	03:30	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
11/23/2022	03:45	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11/23/2022	04:00	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
11/23/2022	04:15	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11/23/2022	04:30	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11/23/2022	04:45	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
11/23/2022	05:00	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
11/23/2022	05:15	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
11/23/2022	05:30	0	0	0	0	0	0	3
11/23/2022	05:45	0	0	0	0	0	1	2
11/23/2022	06:00	0	0	0	0	0	1	1
11/23/2022	06:15	0	0	0	0	0	1	2
11/23/2022	06:30	0	0	0	0	0	0	4
11/23/2022	06:45	0	0	0	0	0	1	2
11/23/2022	07:00	0	0	0	0	0	0	7
11/23/2022	07:15	0	0	0	1	0	0	3
11/23/2022	07:30	1	1	0	0	0	1	7
11/23/2022	07:45	0	0	0	1	1	0	7
11/23/2022	08:00	0	0	0	0	0	1	5
11/23/2022	08:15	0	0	0	0	0	4	2
11/23/2022	08:30	0	0	0	0	1	1	7
11/23/2022	08:45	0	0	0	0	2	0	4
11/23/2022	09:00	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
11/23/2022	09:15	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
11/23/2022	09:30	0	0	0	0	0	0	4
11/23/2022	09:45	0	0	0	0	1	0	0
11/23/2022	10:00	0	1	0	0	0	2	2
11/23/2022	10:15	0	0	0	0	0	0	4
11/23/2022	10:30	0	0	0	0	1	0	2
11/23/2022	10:45	0	0	0	0	0	0	4
11/23/2022	11:00	0	0	0	0	0	1	7
11/23/2022	11:15	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
11/23/2022	11:30	0	0	0	0	0	2	1
11/23/2022	11:45	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
11/23/2022	12:00	0	0	0	0	1	0	1
11/23/2022	12:15	0	0	0	0	0	0	5
11/23/2022	12:30	0	0	0	0	0	0	3
11/23/2022	12:45	1	0	0	0	0	0	6
11/23/2022	13:00	0	0	0	0	0	0	3
11/23/2022	13:15	0	0	0	0	0	0	4
11/23/2022	13:30	0	0	0	0	0	1	2
11/23/2022	13:45	0	0	0	0	1	0	2
11/23/2022	14:00	0	0	0	0	0	1	2
11/23/2022	14:15	0	0	2	0	0	0	0
11/23/2022	14:30	1	0	0	0	0	0	2

11/23/2022	14:45	0	0	0	0	0	1	6
11/23/2022	15:00	0	0	0	0	1	0	7
11/23/2022	15:15	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
11/23/2022	15:30	0	0	1	0	1	3	3
11/23/2022	15:45	0	0	0	0	0	1	4
11/23/2022	16:00	0	0	0	0	4	2	0
11/23/2022	16:15	0	0	0	0	0	0	6
11/23/2022	16:30	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
11/23/2022	16:45	0	0	0	0	0	2	5
11/23/2022	17:00	0	1	0	0	2	3	4
11/23/2022	17:15	0	0	0	1	0	1	10
11/23/2022	17:30	0	0	0	0	0	0	4
11/23/2022	17:45	0	0	1	0	0	0	4
11/23/2022	18:00	0	0	0	0	0	2	5
11/23/2022	18:15	0	0	0	0	0	0	4
11/23/2022	18:30	0	0	0	0	0	0	5
11/23/2022	18:45	0	0	0	0	0	0	4
11/23/2022	19:00	0	1	0	0	0	1	2
11/23/2022	19:15	0	0	0	0	0	2	3
11/23/2022	19:30	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
11/23/2022	19:45	0	0	0	0	0	1	3
11/23/2022	20:00	0	0	0	0	0	1	1
11/23/2022	20:15	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
11/23/2022	20:30	0	0	0	0	1	0	4
11/23/2022	20:45	0	0	0	0	0	1	4
11/23/2022	21:00	0	1	0	0	0	0	1
11/23/2022	21:15	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
11/23/2022	21:30	0	0	0	0	0	0	5
11/23/2022	21:45	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
11/23/2022	22:00	0	0	0	0	0	0	4
11/23/2022	22:15	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
11/23/2022	22:30	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11/23/2022	22:45	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
11/23/2022	23:00	0	0	0	0	0	1	1
11/23/2022	23:15	0	0	0	0	1	1	0
11/23/2022	23:30	0	0	0	0	0	1	1
11/23/2022	23:45	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
24 Hr Summary		3	6	4	3	18	46	231

Date	Starting Hr:min	<15	15 to <20	20 to <25	25 to <30	30 to <35	35 to <40	40 to <45
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11/24/2022	00:15	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11/24/2022	00:30	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11/24/2022	00:45	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
11/24/2022	01:00	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11/24/2022	01:15	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11/24/2022	01:30	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11/24/2022	01:45	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11/24/2022	02:00	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
11/24/2022	02:15	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11/24/2022	02:30	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
11/24/2022	02:45	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11/24/2022	03:00	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11/24/2022	03:15	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

11/24/2022	03:30	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11/24/2022	03:45	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11/24/2022	04:00	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11/24/2022	04:15	0	0	0	1	0	0	0
11/24/2022	04:30	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11/24/2022	04:45	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
11/24/2022	05:00	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11/24/2022	05:15	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11/24/2022	05:30	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11/24/2022	05:45	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11/24/2022	06:00	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
11/24/2022	06:15	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
11/24/2022	06:30	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
11/24/2022	06:45	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11/24/2022	07:00	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
11/24/2022	07:15	1	0	0	0	1	0	3
11/24/2022	07:30	0	0	0	1	0	0	2
11/24/2022	07:45	0	0	0	0	0	1	9
11/24/2022	08:00	0	0	0	0	0	1	2
11/24/2022	08:15	1	1	0	0	0	0	2
11/24/2022	08:30	0	1	0	0	1	0	4
11/24/2022	08:45	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11/24/2022	09:00	0	0	0	0	0	0	3
11/24/2022	09:15	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
11/24/2022	09:30	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
11/24/2022	09:45	0	0	0	0	0	0	3
11/24/2022	10:00	0	1	0	0	0	1	3
11/24/2022	10:15	0	0	0	0	0	0	3
11/24/2022	10:30	0	0	0	0	0	2	2
11/24/2022	10:45	0	0	0	0	0	2	5
11/24/2022	11:00	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
11/24/2022	11:15	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
11/24/2022	11:30	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
11/24/2022	11:45	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11/24/2022	12:00	0	0	0	0	0	2	1
11/24/2022	12:15	0	0	0	0	0	0	6
11/24/2022	12:30	0	0	0	0	0	1	3
11/24/2022	12:45	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11/24/2022	13:00	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
11/24/2022	13:15	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
11/24/2022	13:30	0	0	0	0	0	0	4
11/24/2022	13:45	1	0	0	0	0	1	2
11/24/2022	14:00	0	0	0	0	0	0	6
11/24/2022	14:15	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
11/24/2022	14:30	0	0	0	0	0	1	3
11/24/2022	14:45	0	0	0	0	0	0	3
11/24/2022	15:00	0	0	0	1	1	0	6
11/24/2022	15:15	0	1	0	0	0	0	1
11/24/2022	15:30	0	0	0	0	0	7	8
11/24/2022	15:45	0	1	0	0	0	1	5
11/24/2022	16:00	0	0	0	0	2	1	4
11/24/2022	16:15	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
11/24/2022	16:30	0	0	0	0	1	5	3
11/24/2022	16:45	0	0	0	0	0	0	4

11/24/2022	17:00	0	0	0	0	1	2	5
11/24/2022	17:15	0	0	0	0	0	1	5
11/24/2022	17:30	0	0	0	0	0	2	1
11/24/2022	17:45	0	0	0	1	0	1	3
11/24/2022	18:00	1	0	0	0	0	1	5
11/24/2022	18:15	1	0	0	0	0	0	6
11/24/2022	18:30	0	0	0	0	0	0	3
11/24/2022	18:45	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
11/24/2022	19:00	0	0	1	0	0	0	3
11/24/2022	19:15	0	0	0	0	0	0	3
11/24/2022	19:30	0	0	0	1	0	0	4
11/24/2022	19:45	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11/24/2022	20:00	0	0	0	0	0	1	3
11/24/2022	20:15	0	0	0	0	0	0	3
11/24/2022	20:30	0	0	0	0	0	1	1
11/24/2022	20:45	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
11/24/2022	21:00	0	0	0	0	0	0	3
11/24/2022	21:15	0	0	0	0	1	0	1
11/24/2022	21:30	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11/24/2022	21:45	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11/24/2022	22:00	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
11/24/2022	22:15	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
11/24/2022	22:30	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11/24/2022	22:45	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
11/24/2022	23:00	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
11/24/2022	23:15	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
11/24/2022	23:30	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11/24/2022	23:45	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
24 Hr Summary		5	7	1	5	8	37	178

45 to <50	50 to <55	55 to <60	60 to <65	65 to <70	70 to <75	75 to <80	80 to <85	85 to <90
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2	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0
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0	7	6	0	0	1	0	0	0
4	7	8	3	0	0	0	0	0
6	12	19	3	3	0	0	0	0
8	16	18	3	4	1	1	0	0
16	12	17	2	1	0	0	0	0
10	30	29	2	2	0	0	0	0
17	29	22	7	3	0	0	0	0
36	48	29	10	2	0	0	0	0
15	49	19	11	0	0	0	0	0
13	41	22	4	3	3	0	0	0
16	41	32	15	1	0	0	0	0
9	40	47	10	4	0	0	0	0
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6	23	24	7	1	1	1	0	0
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10	33	29	4	1	0	0	0	0
11	26	20	6	1	0	0	0	0
9	22	29	13	1	0	0	0	0
15	31	25	7	1	0	0	0	0
12	27	37	12	3	0	0	0	0
17	38	25	11	2	0	0	0	0
19	27	27	13	2	1	0	0	0

12	32	36	3	2	0	0	0	0
18	42	30	5	3	0	0	0	0
17	41	35	5	3	0	0	0	0
15	31	30	8	3	0	0	0	0
15	32	23	7	2	0	0	0	0
18	30	33	13	2	0	0	0	0
21	31	24	13	1	0	1	0	0
15	47	22	9	1	1	1	0	0
10	26	38	10	2	0	0	0	0
14	41	23	7	3	0	0	0	0
17	51	15	7	4	3	0	0	0
24	50	35	8	0	0	0	0	0
20	45	29	8	2	1	0	0	0
30	57	29	2	2	0	0	0	0
23	41	37	10	2	2	0	0	0
27	65	30	5	3	0	0	0	0
22	49	30	4	0	0	0	0	0
16	38	29	6	2	0	0	0	1
35	51	16	5	1	0	0	0	0
14	42	14	5	0	0	0	0	0
19	31	20	3	1	0	0	0	0
12	24	10	6	0	0	0	0	0
24	31	15	1	1	1	0	0	0
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20	13	14	5	1	0	0	0	0
19	28	7	8	1	0	1	0	0
20	17	8	0	1	0	0	0	0
6	10	6	3	2	0	0	0	0
9	18	11	3	0	0	1	0	0
11	17	6	4	1	0	0	0	0
5	9	8	1	1	0	0	0	0
9	16	9	4	0	1	0	0	0
4	15	6	2	2	0	0	0	0
7	11	5	2	0	0	0	0	0
6	11	3	3	0	0	0	0	0
6	5	6	2	1	0	0	0	0
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3	9	6	3	2	0	0	0	0
5	2	3	0	0	0	0	0	0
3	10	7	1	0	1	0	0	0
5	19	7	1	0	1	0	0	0
5	11	6	1	0	0	0	0	0
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45 to <50	50 to <55	55 to <60	60 to <65	65 to <70	70 to <75	75 to <80	80 to <85	85 to <90
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0	1	3	0	0	0	0	0	0

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0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0
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6	5	7	1	0	0	0	0	0
1	3	3	2	0	0	0	0	0
4	11	4	1	0	0	0	0	0
12	7	8	2	0	0	0	0	0
11	18	13	1	0	0	0	0	0
11	16	7	0	2	0	0	0	0
14	19	16	1	0	0	0	0	0
27	32	25	6	0	0	0	0	0
29	37	31	6	2	1	0	0	0
16	31	16	10	2	0	0	0	0
17	25	25	11	2	1	0	0	0
15	37	28	7	1	0	1	0	0
19	20	24	5	3	0	0	0	0
5	22	18	6	1	0	0	0	0
5	35	21	8	0	0	0	1	0
17	23	25	4	2	0	0	0	0
7	44	24	12	0	0	0	0	0
17	27	22	11	0	1	0	0	0
23	22	11	6	0	0	0	0	0
11	32	15	7	1	1	0	0	0
13	30	33	5	2	0	0	0	0
10	29	24	6	4	1	0	0	0
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13	34	18	3	1	0	0	0	0
8	29	24	6	3	0	0	0	0
12	34	30	10	1	1	0	1	0
18	30	15	7	1	1	0	0	0
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22	43	27	11	3	0	0	0	0
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27	44	27	7	1	0	0	0	0
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24	25	22	3	0	0	0	0	0
17	26	9	6	0	1	0	2	0
8	30	14	7	1	0	0	0	1
12	29	12	3	1	0	0	0	0
10	21	17	4	0	0	0	0	0
6	21	13	3	1	0	0	0	0
10	11	11	3	0	0	0	0	0
9	26	14	2	1	0	0	0	0
6	9	12	2	3	0	0	0	0
6	12	11	1	1	0	0	0	0
13	15	8	1	1	1	0	0	0
10	14	12	2	2	1	0	0	0
4	8	10	1	0	0	0	0	0
2	6	6	1	0	0	0	0	0
4	8	3	3	0	1	0	0	0
2	7	7	1	1	0	0	0	0
2	8	2	1	0	0	0	0	0
3	7	5	1	1	0	0	0	0
5	2	6	2	0	1	0	0	0
4	6	5	2	1	0	0	0	0
7	13	10	3	1	1	0	0	0
4	7	2	2	0	0	0	0	0
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45 to <50	50 to <55	55 to <60	60 to <65	65 to <70	70 to <75	75 to <80	80 to <85	85 to <90
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2	2	7	4	2	0	0	0	0
3	3	3	3	0	0	0	0	0
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17	35	25	9	3	0	0	0	0
31	54	34	5	0	1	1	1	0
16	33	20	10	3	0	0	0	0
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12	41	23	9	0	0	0	0	0
14	37	14	5	1	0	0	0	0
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12	19	29	9	2	0	1	0	0
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16	26	23	7	1	0	0	0	0
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11	27	18	7	0	0	0	0	0
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7	23	24	19	2	0	0	0	0
27	33	22	4	0	0	0	0	0
8	43	32	12	1	0	0	0	0
11	47	32	2	0	1	0	0	0
14	30	26	9	1	2	0	0	0
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10	38	24	4	3	0	0	0	0
12	34	15	12	2	0	0	0	0
15	40	33	13	2	2	0	0	0
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21	53	41	8	2	1	0	0	0
23	46	39	10	2	0	0	0	0
20	34	33	13	3	0	0	0	0
23	56	28	14	2	1	0	0	0
24	57	35	10	1	1	0	0	0
20	66	39	8	2	0	0	0	0
16	41	28	19	2	0	0	0	0
28	46	16	9	0	1	0	0	0

18	39	19	12	0	0	0	0	0
17	38	24	8	1	0	0	0	0
15	31	25	5	1	0	1	0	0
20	38	16	1	0	1	0	0	0
14	32	15	5	0	1	0	0	0
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10	16	9	4	1	0	0	0	0
9	14	12	3	0	0	1	0	0
11	14	9	2	0	0	0	0	0
5	16	9	6	2	0	0	0	0
4	9	13	3	1	0	0	0	0
7	12	7	5	0	1	0	0	0
8	12	11	0	2	0	0	1	0
9	8	5	8	0	0	0	0	0
0	8	6	3	0	0	0	0	0
3	5	8	4	1	0	0	0	0
2	6	6	2	1	0	0	0	0
2	3	2	7	0	0	0	0	0
5	6	3	3	0	0	0	0	0
3	6	6	2	1	0	0	0	0
5	10	9	1	1	0	0	0	0
8	6	10	4	1	1	0	0	0
2	2	6	1	0	0	0	0	0
2	7	6	1	1	1	0	0	0
855	1982	1448	525	86	19	5	3	0

022-12-00-AM to Thu-Nov-24-2022-11-59-PM

90 to <95	95 to <100	100 to <105	105 to <110	110 to <115	115 to >120	Total Counts
0	0	0	0	0	0	4
0	0	0	0	0	0	8
0	0	0	0	0	0	4
0	0	0	0	0	0	4
0	0	0	0	0	0	4
0	0	0	0	0	0	1
0	0	0	0	0	0	5
0	0	0	0	0	0	2
0	0	0	0	0	0	2
0	0	0	0	0	0	5
0	0	0	0	0	0	5
0	0	0	0	0	0	1
0	0	0	0	0	0	4
0	0	0	0	0	0	3
0	0	0	0	0	0	2
0	0	0	0	0	0	4
0	0	0	0	0	0	1
0	0	0	0	0	0	3
0	0	0	0	0	0	5
0	0	0	0	0	0	5
0	0	0	0	0	0	16
0	0	0	0	0	0	17
0	0	0	0	0	0	11
0	0	0	0	0	0	28
0	0	0	0	0	0	14
0	0	0	0	0	0	24
0	0	0	0	0	0	43
0	0	0	0	0	0	52
0	0	0	0	0	0	55
0	0	0	0	0	0	76
0	0	0	0	0	0	92
0	1	1	0	0	0	140
0	0	0	0	0	0	102
0	0	0	0	0	0	88
0	0	0	0	0	0	109
0	0	0	0	0	0	115
0	0	0	0	0	0	74
0	0	0	0	0	0	69
0	0	0	0	0	0	79
0	0	0	0	0	0	92
0	0	0	0	0	0	77
0	0	0	0	0	0	70
0	0	0	0	0	0	66
0	0	0	0	0	0	77
0	0	0	0	0	0	66
0	0	0	0	0	0	76
0	0	0	0	0	0	82
0	0	0	0	0	0	93
0	0	0	0	0	0	95
0	0	0	0	0	0	93

0	0	0	0	0	0	91
0	0	0	0	0	0	105
0	0	0	0	0	0	104
0	0	0	0	0	0	91
0	0	0	0	0	0	83
0	0	0	0	0	0	100
0	0	0	0	0	0	95
0	0	0	0	0	0	104
0	0	0	0	0	0	90
0	0	0	0	0	0	91
0	0	0	0	0	0	106
0	0	0	0	0	0	126
0	0	0	0	0	0	115
0	0	0	0	0	0	128
0	0	0	0	0	0	122
0	0	0	0	0	0	134
0	0	0	0	0	0	113
0	0	0	0	0	0	103
0	0	0	0	0	0	121
0	0	0	0	0	0	81
0	0	0	0	0	0	84
0	0	0	0	0	0	55
0	0	0	0	0	0	80
0	0	0	0	0	0	70
0	0	0	0	0	0	49
0	0	0	0	0	0	63
0	0	0	0	0	0	55
0	0	0	0	0	0	65
0	0	0	0	0	0	50
0	0	0	0	0	0	28
0	0	0	0	0	0	42
0	0	0	0	0	0	40
0	0	0	0	0	0	28
0	0	0	0	0	0	44
0	0	0	0	0	0	30
0	0	0	0	0	0	27
0	0	0	0	0	0	23
0	0	0	0	0	0	21
0	0	0	0	0	0	23
0	0	0	0	0	0	27
0	0	0	0	0	0	11
0	0	0	0	0	0	24
0	0	0	0	0	0	36
0	0	0	0	0	0	28
0	0	0	0	0	0	16
0	0	0	0	0	0	16
0	1	1	0	0	0	5301

90 to <95	95 to <100	100 to <105	105 to <110	110 to <115	115 to >120	Total Counts
0	0	0	0	0	0	6
0	0	0	0	0	0	3
0	0	0	0	0	0	6
0	0	0	0	0	0	4
0	0	0	0	0	0	4

0	0	0	0	0	0	2
0	0	0	0	0	0	2
0	0	0	0	0	0	2
0	0	0	0	0	0	1
0	0	0	0	0	0	3
0	0	0	0	0	0	3
0	0	0	0	0	0	3
0	0	0	0	0	0	1
0	0	0	0	0	0	1
0	0	0	0	0	0	6
0	0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	0	2
0	0	0	0	0	0	6
0	0	0	0	0	0	3
0	0	0	0	0	0	8
0	0	0	0	0	0	7
0	0	0	0	0	0	15
0	0	0	0	0	0	12
0	0	0	0	0	0	22
0	0	0	0	0	0	11
0	0	0	0	0	0	23
0	0	0	0	0	0	33
0	0	0	0	0	0	46
0	0	0	0	0	0	43
0	0	0	0	0	0	54
0	0	0	0	0	0	100
0	0	0	0	0	0	115
0	0	0	0	0	0	81
0	0	0	0	0	0	87
0	0	0	0	0	0	98
0	0	0	0	0	0	77
0	0	0	0	0	0	53
0	0	0	0	0	0	71
0	0	0	0	0	0	75
0	0	0	0	0	0	88
0	0	0	0	0	0	83
0	0	0	0	0	0	66
0	0	0	0	0	0	70
0	0	0	0	0	0	87
0	0	0	0	0	0	82
0	0	0	0	0	0	82
0	0	0	0	0	0	72
0	0	0	0	0	0	72
0	0	0	0	0	0	91
0	0	0	0	0	0	77
0	0	0	0	0	0	82
0	0	0	0	0	0	104
0	0	0	0	0	0	91
0	0	0	0	0	0	79
0	0	0	0	0	0	69
0	0	0	0	0	0	92
0	0	0	0	0	0	109
0	0	0	0	0	0	100
0	0	0	0	1	0	106

0	0	0	0	0	0	100
0	0	0	0	0	0	96
0	0	0	0	0	0	134
0	0	0	0	0	0	114
0	0	0	0	0	0	116
0	0	0	0	0	0	106
0	0	0	0	0	0	106
0	0	0	0	0	0	104
0	0	0	0	0	0	113
0	0	0	0	0	0	88
0	0	0	0	0	0	92
0	0	0	0	0	0	75
0	0	0	0	0	0	85
0	0	0	0	0	0	82
0	0	0	0	0	0	78
0	0	0	0	0	0	66
0	0	0	0	0	0	65
0	0	0	0	0	0	61
0	0	0	0	0	0	57
0	0	0	0	0	0	45
0	0	0	0	0	0	39
0	0	0	0	0	0	54
0	0	0	0	0	0	33
0	0	0	0	0	0	36
0	0	0	0	0	0	44
0	0	0	0	0	0	43
0	0	0	0	0	0	25
0	0	0	0	0	0	20
0	0	0	0	0	0	20
0	0	0	0	0	0	22
0	0	0	0	0	0	15
0	0	0	0	0	0	17
0	0	0	0	0	0	17
0	0	0	0	0	0	20
0	0	0	0	0	0	37
0	0	0	0	0	0	17
0	0	0	0	0	0	14
0	0	0	0	1	0	5047

90 to <95	95 to <100	100 to <105	105 to <110	110 to <115	115 to >120	Total Counts
0	0	0	0	0	0	7
0	0	0	0	0	0	4
0	0	0	0	0	0	7
0	0	0	0	0	0	7
0	0	0	0	0	0	4
0	0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	0	5
0	0	0	0	0	0	2
0	0	0	0	0	0	5
0	0	0	0	0	0	2
0	0	0	0	0	0	3
0	0	0	0	0	0	1
0	0	0	0	0	0	2
0	0	0	0	0	0	3

0	0	0	0	0	0	7
0	0	0	0	0	0	4
0	0	0	0	0	0	2
0	0	0	0	0	0	6
0	0	0	0	0	0	5
0	0	0	0	0	0	9
0	0	0	0	0	0	5
0	0	0	0	0	0	17
0	0	0	0	0	0	12
0	0	0	0	0	0	16
0	0	0	0	0	0	11
0	0	0	0	0	0	25
0	0	0	0	0	0	39
0	0	0	0	0	0	39
0	0	0	0	0	0	45
0	0	0	0	0	0	55
0	0	0	0	0	0	92
0	0	0	0	0	0	137
0	0	0	0	0	0	85
0	0	0	0	0	0	73
0	0	0	0	0	0	91
0	0	0	0	0	0	71
0	0	0	0	0	0	60
0	0	0	0	0	0	66
0	0	0	0	0	0	74
0	0	0	0	0	0	97
0	0	0	0	0	0	78
0	0	0	0	0	0	78
0	0	0	0	0	0	79
0	0	0	0	0	0	83
0	0	0	0	0	0	64
0	0	0	0	0	0	83
0	0	0	0	0	0	88
0	0	0	0	0	0	99
0	0	0	0	0	0	82
0	0	0	0	0	0	81
0	0	0	0	0	0	90
0	0	0	0	0	0	96
0	0	0	0	0	0	94
0	0	0	0	0	0	84
0	0	0	0	0	0	100
0	0	0	0	0	0	83
0	0	0	0	0	0	81
0	0	0	0	0	0	106
0	0	0	0	0	0	102
0	0	0	0	0	0	92
0	0	0	0	0	0	134
0	0	0	0	0	0	122
0	0	0	0	0	0	118
0	0	0	0	0	0	131
0	0	0	0	0	0	135
0	0	0	0	0	0	137
0	0	0	0	0	0	115
0	0	0	0	0	0	104

0	0	0	0	0	0	96
0	0	0	0	0	0	94
0	0	0	0	0	0	81
0	0	0	0	0	0	81
0	0	0	0	0	0	74
0	0	0	0	0	0	76
0	0	0	0	0	0	48
0	0	0	0	0	0	63
0	0	0	0	0	0	69
0	0	0	0	0	0	53
0	0	0	0	0	0	45
0	0	0	0	0	0	39
0	0	0	0	0	0	40
0	0	0	0	0	0	41
0	0	0	0	0	0	32
0	0	0	0	0	0	33
0	0	0	0	0	0	37
0	0	0	0	0	0	32
0	0	0	0	0	0	17
0	0	0	0	0	0	21
0	0	0	0	0	0	18
0	0	0	0	0	0	15
0	0	0	0	0	0	17
0	0	0	0	0	0	20
0	0	0	0	0	0	27
0	0	0	0	0	0	31
0	0	0	0	0	0	11
0	0	0	0	0	0	19
0	0	0	0	0	0	5164

Avg Speed (km/h)	85pct Speed	10km/h Pace	% in pace	# of Speeders	% Speeders	VEH_SM
-1	52	42 to 52	75.0	2	50.0	0
-1	60	52 to 62	75.0	6	75.0	0
-1	54	44 to 54	75.0	2	50.0	0
53.8	57	48 to 58	100.0	3	75.0	0
-1	56	46 to 56	75.0	2	50.0	0
-1	50	40 to 50	100.0	0	0	0
-1	52	42 to 52	80.0	3	60.0	0
52.3	54	44 to 54	100.0	2	100.0	0
-1	51	41 to 51	100.0	1	50.0	0
-1	58	54 to 64	60.0	3	60.0	0
-1	53	43 to 53	80.0	3	60.0	0
51.8	38	28 to 38	100.0	0	0	0
-1	57	47 to 57	75.0	3	75.0	0
-1	62	52 to 62	100.0	3	100.0	0
-1	61	39 to 49	50.0	1	50.0	0
56.5	58	52 to 62	75.0	3	75.0	0
-1	54	44 to 54	100.0	1	100.0	0
-1	72	37 to 47	33.3	2	66.7	0
-1	51.7	42 to 52	100.0	3	60.0	0
55.1	53	43 to 53	80.0	3	60.0	0
-1	59	46 to 56	68.8	9	56.3	0
-1	60	51 to 61	70.6	13	76.5	0
-1	59	49 to 59	72.7	10	90.9	0
54.3	59	47 to 57	78.6	21	75.0	0
-1	57	48 to 58	92.9	14	100.0	0
-1	58	49 to 59	62.5	15	62.5	0
-1	59	48 to 58	74.4	35	81.4	1
54.9	59.5	49 to 59	71.2	42	80.8	0
-1	57.3	47 to 57	65.5	32	58.2	2
-1	56.6	48 to 58	84.2	56	73.7	0
-1	57.3	46 to 56	62.0	54	58.7	0
52.2	56.8	47 to 57	74.3	81	57.9	0
-1	57.2	47 to 57	72.5	71	69.6	0
-1	57.5	48 to 58	76.1	69	78.4	0
-1	59	50 to 60	70.6	83	76.1	0
53.6	58	51 to 61	80.9	100	87.0	0
-1	58.7	50 to 60	82.4	62	83.8	0
-1	59	49 to 59	71.0	53	76.8	0
-1	58.8	46 to 56	68.4	58	73.4	0
53.6	57.4	46 to 56	73.9	62	67.4	1
-1	59.5	50 to 60	71.4	60	77.9	0
-1	58	48 to 58	74.3	51	72.9	0
-1	58.5	49 to 59	74.2	46	69.7	0
53.8	57.5	49 to 59	84.4	61	79.2	0
-1	58.4	49 to 59	74.2	51	77.3	0
-1	59.8	50 to 60	72.4	62	81.6	0
-1	57.6	48 to 58	73.2	62	75.6	0
54	59.2	49 to 59	74.2	75	80.6	0
-1	58.7	47 to 57	77.9	69	72.6	0
-1	60.2	47 to 57	65.6	62	66.7	0

-1	58	49 to 59	82.4	70	76.9	0
53.3	57.2	48 to 58	74.3	72	68.6	1
-1	56.9	48 to 58	76.9	78	75.0	1
-1	58.4	48 to 58	70.3	67	73.6	1
-1	57.5	47 to 57	74.7	62	74.7	0
53.6	59	48 to 58	71.0	74	74.0	0
-1	59.2	47 to 57	67.4	66	69.5	0
-1	57	46 to 56	72.1	72	69.2	0
-1	58.5	49 to 59	76.7	73	81.1	0
53.4	57.3	48 to 58	76.9	67	73.6	0
-1	58	46 to 56	72.6	74	69.8	0
-1	56.8	49 to 59	76.2	85	67.5	1
-1	57	47 to 57	73.9	76	66.1	0
52.3	55.7	47 to 57	81.3	84	65.6	1
-1	57.9	48 to 58	74.6	87	71.3	0
-1	55.8	46 to 56	80.6	97	72.4	0
-1	56.5	48 to 58	78.8	74	65.5	0
52.6	57.4	48 to 58	68.9	71	68.9	0
-1	54.7	45 to 55	76.0	60	49.6	1
-1	55.8	48 to 58	80.2	57	70.4	0
-1	55.9	48 to 58	71.4	50	59.5	0
51.3	58	45 to 55	70.9	34	61.8	0
-1	56	44 to 54	72.5	47	58.8	1
-1	55.9	48 to 58	78.6	46	65.7	0
-1	56.3	48 to 58	81.6	31	63.3	0
52.2	59.6	47 to 57	71.4	42	66.7	0
-1	58	47 to 57	74.5	32	58.2	0
-1	58	45 to 55	75.4	37	56.9	0
-1	54.7	45 to 55	80.0	22	44.0	0
51.9	59.5	50 to 60	64.3	19	67.9	0
-1	58	47 to 57	76.2	31	73.8	0
-1	57.5	46 to 56	77.5	25	62.5	0
-1	55	46 to 56	78.6	17	60.7	0
52.3	57	47 to 57	70.5	29	65.9	0
-1	59	47 to 57	76.7	21	70.0	0
-1	55.5	46 to 56	77.8	17	63.0	0
-1	58	47 to 57	82.6	16	69.6	0
52.6	59	47 to 57	61.9	13	61.9	0
-1	56	47 to 57	78.3	11	47.8	0
-1	61	48 to 58	59.3	18	66.7	0
-1	55.5	43 to 53	72.7	4	36.4	0
52	57	50 to 60	75.0	18	75.0	0
-1	56.5	48 to 58	80.6	23	63.9	0
-1	56.7	44 to 54	67.9	17	60.7	0
-1	61	47 to 57	62.5	12	75.0	0
52.5	59.7	50 to 60	81.3	11	68.8	0
13.2	58	48 to 58	71.7	3694	69.7	11

Avg Speed (km/h)	85pct Speed	10km/h Pace	% in pace	# of Speeders	% Speeders	VEH_SM
-1	56	47 to 57	83.3	3	50.0	0
-1	59	49 to 59	100.0	2	66.7	0
-1	56	46 to 56	66.7	5	83.3	0
51.9	49	43 to 53	100.0	1	25.0	0
-1	55	47 to 57	100.0	4	100.0	0

-1	52	42 to 52	100.0	1	50.0	0
-1	56	46 to 56	100.0	1	50.0	0
52.9	60	31 to 41	50.0	1	50.0	0
-1	71	61 to 71	100.0	1	100.0	0
-1	58	48 to 58	66.7	2	66.7	0
-1	55	35 to 45	66.7	1	33.3	0
52.7	56	46 to 56	100.0	2	66.7	0
-1	68	58 to 68	100.0	1	100.0	0
-1	47	37 to 47	100.0	0	0	0
-1	60	40 to 50	50.0	3	50.0	0
0	0	0	0	0	0	0
-1	50	40 to 50	100.0	0	0	0
-1	60	45 to 55	66.7	5	83.3	0
-1	54	44 to 54	100.0	2	66.7	0
52.9	56	46 to 56	75.0	6	75.0	0
-1	63	54 to 64	71.4	5	71.4	0
-1	62.5	49 to 59	53.3	10	66.7	0
-1	55	47 to 57	66.7	6	50.0	0
51.8	57	46 to 56	68.2	12	54.5	0
-1	57	47 to 57	63.6	8	72.7	0
-1	55.5	46 to 56	73.9	14	60.9	0
-1	56	46 to 56	69.7	17	51.5	0
51.4	56.7	49 to 59	76.1	28	60.9	0
-1	55	43 to 53	74.4	22	51.2	0
-1	56.5	47 to 57	79.6	34	63.0	0
-1	56.2	47 to 57	76.0	57	57.0	0
51.4	56.5	47 to 57	72.2	70	60.9	0
-1	59	48 to 58	67.9	54	66.7	0
-1	59.2	47 to 57	70.1	62	71.3	0
-1	57.4	48 to 58	74.5	67	68.4	0
52.9	57.7	48 to 58	64.9	48	62.3	0
-1	58	51 to 61	81.1	45	84.9	0
-1	58.3	50 to 60	83.1	61	85.9	0
-1	56.8	48 to 58	85.3	52	69.3	0
53.9	58.5	50 to 60	81.8	71	80.7	0
-1	59	47 to 57	68.7	54	65.1	0
-1	56.7	43 to 53	71.2	36	54.5	0
-1	58.5	50 to 60	71.4	49	70.0	0
52.7	57.6	50 to 60	74.7	63	72.4	1
-1	58.8	50 to 60	68.3	60	73.2	0
-1	57.4	48 to 58	81.7	55	67.1	0
-1	56.8	48 to 58	80.6	49	68.1	1
53.4	58.5	50 to 60	76.4	59	81.9	0
-1	58.8	49 to 59	75.8	73	80.2	0
-1	56.8	47 to 57	68.8	50	64.9	0
-1	59	50 to 60	75.6	68	82.9	0
53.3	56.9	47 to 57	74.0	65	62.5	0
-1	58.5	47 to 57	76.9	66	72.5	0
-1	58.7	51 to 61	70.9	62	78.5	0
-1	57.7	47 to 57	69.6	45	65.2	0
53.3	56.6	47 to 57	82.6	67	72.8	0
-1	58	47 to 57	75.2	80	73.4	0
-1	59	49 to 59	71.0	74	74.0	0
-1	57.5	47 to 57	78.3	70	66.0	1

53.4	56.8	48 to 58	77.0	75	75.0	0
-1	56.2	48 to 58	79.2	61	63.5	0
-1	58.2	49 to 59	77.6	90	67.2	1
-1	56.8	47 to 57	75.4	77	67.5	0
52.6	57	48 to 58	78.4	69	59.5	0
-1	58.3	49 to 59	78.3	85	80.2	0
-1	56	46 to 56	78.3	79	74.5	0
-1	58.7	49 to 59	78.8	85	81.7	0
53.1	57.4	46 to 56	71.7	68	60.2	0
-1	56.3	48 to 58	73.9	57	64.8	1
-1	56.2	48 to 58	70.7	55	59.8	0
-1	58.3	46 to 56	72.0	53	70.7	0
51.9	56.8	46 to 56	74.1	52	61.2	0
-1	58	49 to 59	74.4	60	73.2	0
-1	56	45 to 55	73.1	47	60.3	0
-1	58	48 to 58	71.2	43	65.2	0
52.9	58	48 to 58	75.4	48	73.8	0
-1	55.5	46 to 56	80.3	40	65.6	0
-1	57.2	48 to 58	71.9	38	66.7	0
-1	57	48 to 58	77.8	32	71.1	0
52.2	57	45 to 55	66.7	22	56.4	0
-1	56.5	48 to 58	83.3	34	63.0	0
-1	59	48 to 58	69.7	25	75.8	0
-1	58	49 to 59	72.2	23	63.9	0
52.5	56	47 to 57	72.7	22	50.0	0
-1	57.5	48 to 58	79.1	29	67.4	0
-1	57.2	48 to 58	76.0	19	76.0	0
-1	57.5	49 to 59	65.0	10	50.0	0
52.7	59.5	46 to 56	75.0	14	70.0	0
-1	57	49 to 59	72.7	15	68.2	0
-1	56	43 to 53	80.0	9	60.0	0
-1	57.5	50 to 60	76.5	12	70.6	0
52.8	58	46 to 56	70.6	10	58.8	0
-1	59	47 to 57	65.0	14	70.0	0
-1	58.7	48 to 58	70.3	24	64.9	0
-1	57	44 to 54	70.6	11	64.7	0
53.2	58	48 to 58	78.6	12	85.7	0
13.2	58	48 to 58	72.3	3448	68.3	5

Avg Speed (km/h)	85pct Speed	10km/h Pace	% in pace	# of Speeders	% Speeders	VEH_SM
-1	58	45 to 55	71.4	5	71.4	0
-1	55	45 to 55	75.0	4	100.0	0
-1	56	46 to 56	85.7	6	85.7	0
54	59	49 to 59	71.4	5	71.4	0
-1	55	45 to 55	75.0	3	75.0	0
0	0	0	0	0	0	0
-1	60	50 to 60	80.0	5	100.0	0
55.5	53	43 to 53	100.0	2	100.0	0
-1	58	41 to 51	60.0	3	60.0	0
-1	60	50 to 60	100.0	2	100.0	0
-1	61	41 to 51	66.7	2	66.7	0
52.4	51	41 to 51	100.0	1	100.0	0
-1	57	47 to 57	100.0	2	100.0	0
-1	61	51 to 61	100.0	3	100.0	0

-1	57	47 to 57	85.7	6	85.7	0
54.9	56	47 to 57	100.0	2	50.0	0
-1	57	47 to 57	100.0	2	100.0	0
-1	58	51 to 61	66.7	4	66.7	0
-1	56	46 to 56	80.0	4	80.0	0
54.7	69	50 to 60	66.7	8	88.9	0
-1	53	46 to 56	100.0	2	40.0	0
-1	61	52 to 62	76.5	15	88.2	0
-1	61	52 to 62	75.0	9	75.0	0
55.5	60	50 to 60	81.3	14	87.5	0
-1	56	47 to 57	81.8	9	81.8	0
-1	58	49 to 59	84.0	19	76.0	0
-1	59.5	50 to 60	71.8	31	79.5	0
54.8	58	49 to 59	84.6	31	79.5	0
-1	58	50 to 60	77.8	35	77.8	0
-1	57	48 to 58	74.5	37	67.3	0
-1	58.5	47 to 57	72.8	64	69.6	0
52.7	56.2	47 to 57	78.1	88	64.2	0
-1	59	48 to 58	71.8	58	68.2	0
-1	57	47 to 57	76.7	46	63.0	1
-1	56.8	48 to 58	76.9	68	74.7	2
52.7	55.7	47 to 57	85.9	51	71.8	1
-1	57.7	48 to 58	78.3	44	73.3	1
-1	57.8	48 to 58	81.8	48	72.7	0
-1	59.3	49 to 59	68.9	57	77.0	0
54.1	58.5	49 to 59	78.4	79	81.4	0
-1	58	47 to 57	73.1	52	66.7	1
-1	58.8	49 to 59	76.9	59	75.6	0
-1	59	50 to 60	79.7	64	81.0	0
53.2	56.6	48 to 58	74.7	54	65.1	0
-1	57.7	49 to 59	76.6	47	73.4	0
-1	59.8	47 to 57	69.9	62	74.7	0
-1	59.9	51 to 61	80.7	77	87.5	0
54.6	59.5	50 to 60	78.8	82	82.8	0
-1	59	47 to 57	75.6	64	78.0	1
-1	60.8	51 to 61	65.4	64	79.0	1
-1	56	46 to 56	77.8	52	57.8	0
53.8	58.5	49 to 59	81.3	80	83.3	0
-1	56.8	48 to 58	87.2	74	78.7	0
-1	58.5	48 to 58	77.4	64	76.2	0
-1	58.3	49 to 59	74.0	73	73.0	1
53.6	56.9	49 to 59	81.9	64	77.1	0
-1	59.3	48 to 58	70.4	57	70.4	1
-1	59.2	51 to 61	77.4	89	84.0	0
-1	57.6	48 to 58	77.5	73	71.6	1
53.7	59	48 to 58	68.5	65	70.7	0
-1	56.9	48 to 58	77.6	98	73.1	1
-1	58	47 to 57	79.5	90	73.8	0
-1	58.6	50 to 60	62.7	79	66.9	1
52.9	57.8	46 to 56	72.5	96	73.3	0
-1	57.3	48 to 58	77.0	93	68.9	1
-1	56.5	47 to 57	85.4	105	76.6	0
-1	59.6	47 to 57	66.1	82	71.3	0
52.8	57	45 to 55	76.9	65	62.5	0

-1	58.3	46 to 56	68.8	66	68.8	0
-1	57.3	48 to 58	74.5	62	66.0	0
-1	56.9	47 to 57	80.2	59	72.8	0
52.5	55.2	46 to 56	84.0	54	66.7	0
-1	56.6	47 to 57	73.0	47	63.5	0
-1	57.7	49 to 59	69.7	54	71.1	0
-1	58.7	47 to 57	70.8	35	72.9	0
52.5	57	48 to 58	79.4	45	71.4	0
-1	55.8	46 to 56	79.7	44	63.8	0
-1	58.8	49 to 59	71.7	40	75.5	1
-1	58	47 to 57	64.4	27	60.0	0
52.5	57	48 to 58	82.1	28	71.8	0
-1	55	45 to 55	75.0	25	62.5	0
-1	60	50 to 60	65.9	30	73.2	0
-1	57.7	48 to 58	81.3	25	78.1	0
53.2	60	45 to 55	66.7	25	75.8	0
-1	57.5	48 to 58	73.0	26	70.3	0
-1	60.2	46 to 56	62.5	21	65.6	0
-1	59	50 to 60	88.2	16	94.1	0
53.9	60	50 to 60	71.4	17	81.0	0
-1	59	49 to 59	66.7	14	77.8	0
-1	61	53 to 63	73.3	12	80.0	0
-1	59	44 to 54	64.7	12	70.6	0
54.1	58	47 to 57	65.0	14	70.0	0
-1	57.7	48 to 58	77.8	19	70.4	0
-1	59.5	48 to 58	61.3	22	71.0	0
-1	56.8	47 to 57	90.9	9	81.8	0
54	59	46 to 56	68.4	14	73.7	0
13.2	59	48 to 58	72.6	3760	72.8	15

VEH_MED	VEH_LG
4	0
8	0
3	1
3	1
4	0
1	0
4	1
2	0
2	0
5	0
5	0
1	0
4	0
3	0
1	1
4	0
1	0
3	0
5	0
5	0
14	2
17	0
11	0
25	3
13	1
24	0
40	2
50	2
52	1
75	1
87	5
138	2
98	4
82	5
107	3
113	2
72	2
63	6
77	2
87	4
75	2
66	4
65	1
75	2
64	2
73	3
82	0
92	1
90	4
91	3

89	2
103	1
99	4
90	0
81	2
98	2
93	2
102	2
89	1
87	4
105	1
121	4
106	9
125	2
121	1
129	5
110	3
103	0
118	2
79	2
82	2
54	1
78	1
65	5
48	1
63	0
54	1
65	0
48	1
29	0
41	1
40	0
28	0
43	1
30	0
26	1
23	0
21	0
21	1
27	1
11	0
24	0
35	1
28	0
16	0
16	0
5150	140

Page 1

VEH_MED	VEH_LG
6	0
3	0
6	0
4	0
4	0

1	1
2	0
2	0
1	0
3	0
3	0
3	0
1	0
0	1
5	1
0	0
2	0
6	0
3	0
7	1
7	0
15	0
12	0
22	0
10	1
23	0
33	0
45	1
42	1
51	3
96	4
112	3
78	3
83	4
96	2
77	0
49	4
70	1
74	0
87	2
79	4
64	2
67	3
81	5
80	2
82	0
69	2
71	1
89	2
71	6
81	1
101	3
90	1
79	0
67	2
90	2
106	2
99	2
102	3

96	4
96	0
129	4
109	5
115	1
105	1
102	4
104	0
110	3
87	0
92	0
73	2
84	1
81	1
73	5
65	1
65	0
59	1
58	0
43	2
39	0
53	1
33	0
36	0
44	0
43	0
25	0
20	0
19	1
21	1
15	0
17	0
17	0
20	0
36	1
17	0
14	0
4927	115

Page 2

VEH_MED	VEH_LG
7	0
4	0
7	0
7	0
3	1
0	0
5	0
2	0
5	0
2	0
3	0
1	0
2	0
3	0

7	0
3	1
2	0
5	1
5	0
9	0
5	0
17	0
12	0
15	1
9	2
24	1
38	1
37	2
44	1
54	1
88	4
134	3
79	6
71	1
84	5
69	1
57	2
66	0
72	2
95	2
75	2
78	0
78	1
79	4
64	0
82	1
85	3
98	1
79	2
77	3
86	4
92	4
93	1
82	2
96	3
82	1
79	1
103	3
98	3
91	1
130	3
119	3
114	3
129	2
132	1
133	5
112	3
102	2

95	1
93	1
80	1
81	0
70	3
76	1
47	1
62	1
68	1
51	1
44	1
39	0
39	1
41	0
31	1
32	1
37	0
31	1
17	0
21	0
17	1
14	1
16	1
20	0
25	2
31	0
11	0
19	0
5028	121

13 Street S - 8 Avenue S to 9 Avenue S - NB

Daily Volumes

Incoming-Daily Volume for Daily Vehicle Counts

Vehicles

6000

5000

4000

3000

2000

1000

0

Monday

Tuesday

Wednesday

Thursday

Day					
Friday					
Saturday					
Sunday					

Zoom
help

Average Vehicle Speed (km/h) vs. Time [13 Street 5

Zoom help

Vehicle Counts (30 Minutes)

Vehicle Counts vs. Time [13 Street S - 8 Ave

Vehicle Counts vs. Time in Total Vehicles Displayed=15512

15,512 Counts

120 Percentile Counts Vs. Speed for [13 Street S - 8 Avenue S to 9 Avenue S - NB: Incoming]

85th Pct Speed=58.0 km/h
Vehicle # data=15512
11/22/2022 12:00:00 AM to 11/24/2022 11:59:59 PM

(a)

80

100

120

Date&Time	Speed	Class	Direction
11/22/2022 12:00:11 AM	50.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 12:05:01 AM	49.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 12:09:13 AM	52.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 12:12:13 AM	61.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 12:16:24 AM	43.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 12:16:30 AM	42.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 12:21:07 AM	57.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 12:24:37 AM	60.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 12:26:05 AM	53.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 12:28:20 AM	62.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 12:28:27 AM	54.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 12:29:41 AM	60.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 12:32:47 AM	50.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 12:39:57 AM	65.0	Large	Incoming
11/22/2022 12:44:40 AM	48.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 12:44:43 AM	54.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 12:46:52 AM	57.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 12:53:48 AM	58.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 12:54:56 AM	50.0	Large	Incoming
11/22/2022 12:56:14 AM	52.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 1:06:50 AM	49.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 1:07:59 AM	67.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 1:10:43 AM	56.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 1:10:43 AM	48.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 1:27:12 AM	50.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 1:31:57 AM	43.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 1:32:07 AM	52.0	Large	Incoming
11/22/2022 1:39:53 AM	51.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 1:40:43 AM	43.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 1:40:44 AM	63.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 1:45:07 AM	54.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 1:46:20 AM	52.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 2:06:52 AM	51.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 2:11:01 AM	49.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 2:19:09 AM	46.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 2:21:16 AM	58.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 2:24:42 AM	47.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 2:24:55 AM	58.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 2:25:20 AM	64.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 2:30:59 AM	46.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 2:31:00 AM	50.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 2:38:52 AM	61.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 2:43:52 AM	53.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 2:44:50 AM	53.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 2:45:23 AM	38.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 3:06:26 AM	48.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 3:07:12 AM	57.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 3:09:02 AM	53.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 3:13:04 AM	62.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 3:15:26 AM	60.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 3:19:32 AM	61.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 3:22:07 AM	62.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 3:37:44 AM	61.0	Medium	Incoming

11/22/2022 3:40:45 AM	49.0	Large	Incoming
11/22/2022 3:46:03 AM	44.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 3:53:08 AM	58.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 3:56:29 AM	58.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 3:58:05 AM	62.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 4:13:04 AM	54.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 4:21:33 AM	47.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 4:23:48 AM	72.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 4:27:45 AM	60.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 4:38:02 AM	52.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 4:40:33 AM	48.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 4:41:54 AM	52.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 4:42:56 AM	50.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 4:43:32 AM	52.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 4:46:23 AM	49.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 4:49:28 AM	53.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 4:50:27 AM	51.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 4:53:06 AM	49.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 4:54:57 AM	83.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 5:02:48 AM	58.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 5:04:40 AM	50.0	Large	Incoming
11/22/2022 5:04:47 AM	59.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 5:05:43 AM	47.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 5:05:57 AM	43.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 5:06:05 AM	60.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 5:07:56 AM	66.0	Large	Incoming
11/22/2022 5:08:26 AM	50.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 5:08:32 AM	53.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 5:11:25 AM	56.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 5:11:51 AM	48.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 5:12:06 AM	53.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 5:12:14 AM	51.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 5:12:38 AM	47.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 5:12:41 AM	54.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 5:12:52 AM	49.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 5:15:27 AM	56.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 5:17:13 AM	52.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 5:17:50 AM	53.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 5:17:55 AM	64.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 5:18:47 AM	56.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 5:19:54 AM	61.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 5:21:34 AM	51.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 5:22:42 AM	59.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 5:24:04 AM	47.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 5:24:23 AM	60.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 5:24:45 AM	59.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 5:25:48 AM	57.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 5:26:32 AM	60.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 5:27:21 AM	61.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 5:27:52 AM	45.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 5:28:49 AM	46.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 5:29:55 AM	50.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 5:31:31 AM	65.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 5:33:58 AM	59.0	Medium	Incoming

11/22/2022 5:37:15 AM	51.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 5:38:48 AM	53.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 5:39:41 AM	59.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 5:39:59 AM	55.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 5:40:57 AM	48.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 5:42:06 AM	66.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 5:42:13 AM	53.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 5:44:22 AM	52.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 5:44:50 AM	58.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 5:45:09 AM	54.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 5:45:35 AM	54.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 5:46:29 AM	53.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 5:47:46 AM	62.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 5:48:19 AM	50.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 5:48:54 AM	56.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 5:49:12 AM	56.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 5:50:18 AM	47.0	Medium	Incoming
11/22/2022 5:50:29 AM	49.0	Medium	Incoming
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11/24/2022 11:53:41 AM	56.0	Medium	Incoming
11/24/2022 11:53:49 AM	59.0	Large	Incoming
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11/24/2022 10:15:17 PM	47.0	Medium	Incoming
11/24/2022 10:17:32 PM	61.0	Medium	Incoming
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11/24/2022 10:19:28 PM	55.0	Medium	Incoming
11/24/2022 10:21:58 PM	53.0	Medium	Incoming
11/24/2022 10:22:30 PM	63.0	Medium	Incoming
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11/24/2022 10:24:08 PM	53.0	Medium	Incoming
11/24/2022 10:25:46 PM	55.0	Medium	Incoming
11/24/2022 10:25:55 PM	60.0	Medium	Incoming
11/24/2022 10:27:02 PM	64.0	Medium	Incoming
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11/24/2022 10:46:20 PM	55.0	Medium	Incoming
11/24/2022 10:48:04 PM	58.0	Medium	Incoming
11/24/2022 10:48:47 PM	40.0	Medium	Incoming
11/24/2022 10:49:20 PM	51.0	Medium	Incoming
11/24/2022 10:50:28 PM	46.0	Medium	Incoming
11/24/2022 10:53:05 PM	57.0	Medium	Incoming
11/24/2022 10:53:18 PM	47.0	Medium	Incoming
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11/24/2022 10:53:58 PM	51.0	Medium	Incoming
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11/24/2022 10:54:22 PM	52.0	Medium	Incoming
11/24/2022 10:54:39 PM	56.0	Medium	Incoming
11/24/2022 10:57:47 PM	54.0	Medium	Incoming
11/24/2022 10:58:21 PM	57.0	Medium	Incoming
11/24/2022 10:58:27 PM	55.0	Medium	Incoming
11/24/2022 10:59:02 PM	61.0	Medium	Incoming
11/24/2022 10:59:22 PM	52.0	Medium	Incoming
11/24/2022 11:00:31 PM	53.0	Medium	Incoming
11/24/2022 11:00:49 PM	51.0	Medium	Incoming
11/24/2022 11:01:02 PM	53.0	Medium	Incoming
11/24/2022 11:01:33 PM	46.0	Medium	Incoming
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11/24/2022 11:10:38 PM	47.0	Medium	Incoming
11/24/2022 11:11:16 PM	55.0	Medium	Incoming

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11/24/2022 11:14:56 PM	61.0	Medium	Incoming
11/24/2022 11:16:44 PM	49.0	Medium	Incoming
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11/24/2022 11:24:54 PM	63.0	Medium	Incoming
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11/24/2022 11:29:36 PM	54.0	Medium	Incoming
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11/24/2022 11:37:13 PM	51.0	Medium	Incoming
11/24/2022 11:38:12 PM	57.0	Medium	Incoming
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